

Software engineering to sustain a high-performance computing scientific application: QMCPACK

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- QMCPACK is a Quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) framework. QMC methods solve directly the Schrodinger equation
 - Greater accuracy than density functional theory (DFT) methods
 - Greater computational cost.
- Support architectures from laptops through the world's largest supercomputers.
 - Written in C++17 using hybrid parallel approach
- Goal: improve the quality of the software and enable significant refactoring while also keeping the barrier for open-source software contributions low.

Software Improvements - Docker containers

- Docker images provide uniformity across environments used in GitHub Actions CI tests
 - Using the Spack package manager to generate Docker images and leverage its package managing capabilities.
 - Did not use containers for MacOS and GPU runs
- Docker containers enable reproducible virtual testing environments
- OpenMP offload code compiled by LLVM for host CPUs

Strategic CI expansion on GitHub Actions

- Making full utilization of cloud-based GitHub CPU runners in virtual machines (VMs) using our Docker containers
- CI for GPU development via runners hosted at ORNL and equipped with NVIDIA and AMD cards.
 - second-level CI workflow, which must be triggered manually (by authorized members).
- Utilization and failure rates on our CI system covering CPU and GPU test cases

Total workflows

GitHub Actions CI

Self-hosted CI

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Software Improvements - CI expansion

- Add MacOS build
 - where many new users initially experiment with the code
- GPU testing caught several problems before they made it into the mainline development branch.
 - illustrates the importance of having GPU CI, especially around times of high development activity.
 - failures due to the process of upgrading both CI systems without pausing development while issues were resolved.

Failed jobs

GitHub Actions CI

Self-hosted CI

Software Improvements – Test Coverage

- Code coverage using GNU's gcov was added early in the CI migration
- Code coverage has been increasing since the addition of these CI checks from 38% (absolute) to 52%
- Does not include GPU offload cases

Monthly evolution of code line coverage

Software Improvements - Sanitizing critical code paths

- Resolve existing and guard against future memory leaks
 - Address Sanitizer (ASan)
 - ~50 deterministic tests with memory leaks
- Ambiguous ownership of raw pointers in C++03
 - `std::unique_ptr<T, Deleter>`
 - `std::shared_ptr<T>`
- Working with third-party C libraries
 - Recompile libxml2 with ASAN enabled
 - Specify user-supplied deleter

Software Improvements - Code refactoring

- Code refactoring efforts to ensure the sustainability of the scientific efforts around the software.
- Checkpoint-restart: Checkpoint files contain enough data to restart mid-run
 - Written as plain text, XML and HDF5 files
 - Refactoring I/O components in terms of object ownership and lifetime.
 - improved reusability in the interactions with the underlying HDF5 library.
- Legacy driver implementation was completely removed
 - reduction of nearly 40 K lines of code.

Migrate compile time option to runtime

- Binaries qmcpack and qmcpack_complex differ by

```
#ifdef QMC_COMPLEX
    using ValueType = ComplexType;
#else
    using ValueType = RealType;
#endif
```
- Change SPOSet class to SPOSetT<T> template class
 - Update derived classes
 - Using QMC_COMPLEX to minimize changes
 - Modifying 140+ files, 41k+ lines of code

Conclusions

- Modern software practices impact the overall development process of QMCPACK.
- Target quality strategy
 - Measure code test coverage, check memory access
 - Modernize checkpoint-restart, I/O capabilities
 - Migrate compile-time configuration into runtime variants.
- Showcasing value and impact of our work
 - Enriching the RSE community